

Sustainable practices of Green Human Resource Management

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Abstract: To accomplish United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030, adoption of Sustainable practices and environmental preservation has become an inevitable step to be considered while framing future policies and strategies towards Human resource Management. Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices are being incorporated into the day-to-day operations of practically all industries and businesses. The goal of sustainable HRM practices is to strike a balance between communities, workers, and organizations' economic, social, and environmental well-being. This study investigates the necessity of green human resource management and the effectiveness of integrating green HRM techniques in Indian organizations. It also discusses the challenges Indian businesses have while attempting to use green HRM.

Keywords: Sustainable Human Resource Management, Sustainability Practices, Employee Engagement, Green HRM.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable Human Resource Management (SHRM) is about managing the people working in an organization with a life-long view of the business goals and objectives. The HR departments are responsible for overseeing the workers' recruitment plan, training sessions, evaluating employee job performance, and organizing rewards, compensation management, promotions, and benefits, among other people-oriented activities. From its legacy roles set mid-twentieth-century, transaction based human relations movement, the HRM profession has moved on to assume entrepreneurial orientation, strategic positions in international business, mergers and acquisitions, talent development and diversity, and inclusion. Conscious efforts have been made by companies and HR partners worldwide to build HRM models that are green and sustainable. With the measure of success having shifted from being purely based on wealth, concepts like Green HRM and Triple Bottom Line HRM are becoming the centerpiece of discussions on the topic of Human Resources. To understand the link between sustainability and HRM we have done study on one form of HRM i.e. Green HRM that has been adopted by companies.

II. WHAT IS GREEN HRM?

Green HRM practices, according to Anton et al., are the real green HRM programs, processes, and strategies that are implemented in the organizations in order to lessen the negative environmental impacts of the organizations or increase their positive environmental impacts. In the end, it's claimed that implementing green HRM practices will enhance the company's long-term environmental performance. Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) is defined as the utilization of HRM approaches to improvise the utilization of assets inside business associations and support the achievement of natural sustainability (Koshish, 2019). GHRM is essential to reinforce the commitment of HR related practices towards the more years from 2019 till 2021 on various scholar databases. (Angelo et al. 2014) found out that the common green objectives of researched organizations are: usage of garbage recycling, usage of energy reducer equipment and low-energy-consumption light. Most organizations use solar collectors, but none of them use locally grown food. (Bhutto and Auranzeb 2016) found out that the concept of green management is still new approach for organizations, but mainly companies are focused on organizational waste management, recycling and the usage of green products. (Cherian and Jacob, 2012) found out that green HRM practices improve competitive advantage and overall performance by enhanced employee morale, retention of employees, better public image and attracting employees, increased productivity and sustainability

III. CURRENT PRACTICES IN GREEN HRM

In this part of the paper, we briefly describe functions of HRM which are generally considered as traditional and there can be a variety of green practices under each function. The Green HRM process i.e. Green recruitment, performance management and appraisal, training and development, employee relation, pay and reward and employee exit. We summarize of the existing and certain new green HRM practices under each function of Green HRM.

A. Green Human Resource Planning

At present, some companies engage in forecasting number of employees and types of employees, needed to implement corporate environmental management initiatives/programs/activities (e.g. ISO 14001, cleaner production, responsible care etc.) These are good practices some leading companies have adopted to manage their environmental issues. The corporate environmental management initiatives demand some new job positions and specific set of skills. Green Human Resource Planning gets required in this context. In addition, these companies engage in deciding strategies to meet the forecasted demand for environmental works (e.g. appointing consultants/experts to perform energy or environmental audits) and sometimes they are outsourcing. As far as existing literature is concerned, it did not clearly specify the practices under the function of Green Human Resource Planning. However, based on the observations of the industries and organizations, it is possible to identify certain Green Human Resource Planning Practices. (Lakshmi, n.d.)

B. Recruitment and Selection:

This function involves picking up the most inventive and creative workers and attracting the right talent that will match the organization's green objectives. This requires environment-related questions during interviews, and recruit candidates having green awareness and knowledge. (Tomer & Rana, 2020) The process of employing new employees, who are knowledgeable of environmentally friendly practices and, environmental concerns, as well as the language of preservation and sustainable environmental policies, is known as green recruitment. To proficiently perform environmental management inside the company, institutions should ensure that new talent is conversant with green practices and environmental systems. (Bharani, 2023)

C. Training and Development:

Employee training and development programs should include social and environmental issues at all levels, from technical health and safety considerations on the shop floor, to strategic sustainability issues at executive management and board level (Mandip, 2012). Green orientation programs for the newly higher employees should be an integral part of the training and development process. To sustain in the race market, it is very necessary to each and every organization to change themselves with the change in the scenario and it is more important for every organization to resist that change and that resistance to change will be done by training and development. Training and development are a practice that directing a great deal of attention on development of employee skills and knowledge that relate to specific useful competencies, environmental training also prevent decline of environmental management skill, knowledge and attitudes (Zoogah 2011).

D. Performance Management:

Performance management (PM) is the process by which employees are prompted to enhance their professional skills that help to achieve the organizational goals and objectives in a better way. The recognition of the corporate strategy culminates into the PM. Green performance management plays very important role in the effectiveness of green management work over passage of time because they guide employee performance to the environmental performances need by the organization (Jabbour and Santos, 2008). Firms like Tata Group of Companies have installed corporate-wide environmental performance standards (which cover on-site use, waste management, environmental audits and the reduction of waste) to measure environmental performance standards and developing green information systems and audits. Employees are urged to learn more about environmental efforts that contribute to the achievement of the organization's aim and sustainability objective through the use of green performance management. Between a supervisor and an employee, contact has been continuing for the entire year. Performance evaluation is a crucial part of performance management. When an employee practices environmentally friendly conduct, such as turning off the electricity when not needed and turning off the projectors after meetings, the manager can evaluate that employee's performance. This will help make the company more environmentally friendly.

E. Compensation and Benefits:

Compensation and reward are the major elements of HRM process, this element is the most important for maintaining employee interest to that of the organization. The reward policies are focused on attracting, retaining and motivating the employee which lead to the achievement of organizational goal (Teixeira et al., 2013) and improve the organizational commitment (Daily and Hang, 2001). Green reward management is another key function of green HRM. The sustainability of organization's environmental performance is highly dependent on the green reward management practices of the organizations. To motivate managers and non-managerial employees on corporate environmental management initiatives, green reward management has significant contributions. Organizations can practice it in two ways such as financial and non-financial. In some companies' employees are financially (e.g. incentives, bonuses, cash) rewarded for their good environmental performance. In some other companies, employees are non-financially rewarded (awards/special recognitions/honors/prizes) for their good environmental performance. Dow chemical is a very good example of reward and compensation; employees were motivated and given rewards when they came up with innovative waste reduction idea.

IV. EXAMPLES OF LEADING ORGANISATIONS WITH GREEN HRM INITIATIVES:

Sr.No.	Organization	Initiative
1	ITC	Pioneered the use of ozone-treated elemental chlorine-free bleaching technology in paper production.
2	Wipro	Launched the "Eco Eye" program, focused on waste reduction, minimizing hazardous substances, and greening operations.
3	Suzlon Energy	Constructed energy-efficient buildings, uses renewable energy for hot water systems, and promotes green banking initiatives.
4	HCL Technologies	Launched the "Go Green" campaign, collects e-waste, and introduced Antimony & Beryllium-free laptops.
5	TCS	Ranked among the "11th World's Greenest Companies," utilizes waste-to-fuel technology, and promotes sustainability initiatives.

V. IMPACT OF IMPLEMENTATION OF GHRM

Having in mind that the difference between the old and the new approaches of Strategic HRM arises from the different environment in which organizations work (Wright 1992) and the new approach is focused on competitive advantage (Chopra, 2017) or environmental sustainability (Dubois and Dubois, 2012) we argue that companies have begun to transform their strategies into green strategies (Olson, 2008). Hence, building green organizational awareness means eco-friendly environment conciseness towards electricity, energy, paper, pollution, plants, (Deshwal, 2015; Halawi and Zaraket, 2018) and climate, minerals, water, forest (Dubois and Dubois, 2012) and food (Angelo et al., 2014). Furthermore, waste management (Jackson et al., 2011), reducing production and labor costs (Deshwal, 2015; Renwick et al., 2013; Bombiak and Klauska, 2018) are additional important areas that have an influence on building leadership and corporate strategy (Dubois and Dubois, 2012) for enhancing staff consciousness for involvement (Deshwal, 2015) and their motivation (Renwick et al., 2013; Bombiak and Klauska, 2018) towards improving organizational environmental sustainability. In this context "green" SHRM creates organizational green strategy goals and empowers employees to be sustainable, competent, socially responsible and motivated to create eco work office space (Bombiak and Kluska, 2018). Creating new green branding strategy enables sustainable organization (Deshwal, 2015), increased reputation as well as for economic, social, environmental contribution (Bombiak and Kluska, 2018) and a competitive advantage (Deshwal (2015); Chopra, 2017, Almada and Borges, 2018). On the other hand, not all organizations have full implementation of green strategies (Angelo et al., 2014) because the concept of green management is still a new approach for organizations (Bhutto and Auranzeb, 2016).

VI. CONCLUSION

Sustainable HRM goes beyond the benefits mentioned earlier, boosting employee engagement and retention. Employees who feel their company cares about their well-being and the planet experience a stronger sense of purpose and loyalty. This translates to higher job satisfaction, lower turnover, and a more stable, productive workforce. Moreover, focusing on sustainability helps attract and retain top talent. Today's workers increasingly seek employers aligned with their values and committed to social impact. This competitive edge strengthens your employer brand and attracts skilled individuals, further enhancing your organization's success.

VII. FUTURE RESEARCH

- Investigate the long-term effects of sustainable HRM practices on organizational performance.
- Analyze the specific challenges and opportunities of implementing sustainable HRM in different industries and contexts.
- Examine the potential financial benefits of sustainable HRM practices, such as cost savings from energy-efficient operations and reduced turnover rates.
- Explore the role of leadership in driving sustainability initiatives and the impact it has on employee engagement and satisfaction.
- How organizations can effectively integrate both into their overall business strategy.
- Explore the role of technology in facilitating and tracking sustainable HR initiatives.

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